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JAMIYAT IJTIMOYIY MUNOSABATLARINING MA'NAVYI OMILLARI

SPIRITUAL FACTORS OF SOCIAL RELATIONS OF SOCIETY

ДУХОВНЫЕ ФАКТОРЫ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ ОБЩЕСТВА

ANNOTATSIIYA

Ushbu maqolada, jamiyat va ijtimoiy munosabatlarda mavjud bo'lgan ma'naviy omillar haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Qolaversa, jamiyatning tushunchasi, jamiyatning ta'riflari hamda jamiyatning turlari, jamiyatning shakllanish jarayoni haqida ham ma'lumotlar berilgan.

ANNOTATION

This article provides information on the spiritual factors present in society and social relations. Further details are given on the concept of society, definitions of society and types of society, the process of formation of society.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье представлена информация о духовных факторах, присутствующих в обществе и социальных отношениях. Кроме того, дается информация о понятии общества, определениях общества, а также о типах общества, процессе формирования общества.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

jamiyat, kishilik jamiyati, ma'naviyat, ma'naviy omillar.

KEYWORDS

society, personality society, spirituality, spiritual factors.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

общество, общество личности, духовность, духовные факторы.

INTRODUCTION

Since such concepts as society, sociality, social relations, politics are inextricably linked with social policy, the issues of their interpretation and implementation are approached in different ways. First of all, sociability is about society. "Society" has always been regarded as a very comprehensive concept. It can be applied both to voluntary associations of people on the path of some goal, and to communities where lifestyle, activity is reflected in common, due to natural necessity, or material, spiritual need, as well as to national state structures.

When the concept of "society" is defined in one sense, a number of theoretical, methodological and etymological complexities are encountered. First, this concept is very broad in size and content. Secondly, this concept is an abstract, that is, a philosophical category. Thirdly, this concept is dynamic, that is, developmental. Fourth, society is only the subject of the whole set of Social Sciences, without being the subject of philosophy. Fifth, the term "community" can be used in a variety of meanings. Although the meaning of totality, concentration in the core of each one lies, any society is interpreted differently, depending on its composition, activity, purpose. Suppose that the "Red Crescent Society" is a voluntary association United to carry out a certain type of activity, while the "Society of man" reflects a commonality inherent in humanity. In historical sciences, such as "primitive society", "medieval society", "American society" are also used in the sense of a certain stage in the historical development of mankind or a concrete country. [1]

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

As the relationship and activities of human beings are practiced throughout life, as concentration, cooperation become a necessity of living, so does society. Hence, a society of personality is a social need. Plato, recognizing that society is not only one of the necessary conditions for people to unite, but also to live a life, put forward the idea that "people need each other according to their needs." [2, 94] the same point was also pointed out by Farobius in his time.

Since social unity is a vital need, only material need should not be understood here. In the process of their joint activities, people think among themselves, express their mutual feelings. Usually their joint activities are determined by the unity of goals, as well as the proximity of views, unity of relations, feelings. It reflects the fact that people need each other in terms of spiritual need [3, 464].

Likewise, Empidocles, who lived from 341-270 BC, believes that "men consciously organize to make their own lives. "Arastu advances the idea that society is the "derivative of nature", the medieval philosophy - that God created. Farobius explains the emergence of society in Teleology - from a predetermined purposeful point of view - believes that society is necessary for people to achieve perfection. A number of definitions and approaches can be found in the analysis of the concept of society. Society is the product of such mutual social relations between people, interaction, which is the result of sociality (M. Weber); society is a system of such relations between people that its unifying basis is values and norms (T. Parsons). According to the German philosopher Max Weber (1864-1920), society is a system made up of human interaction, i.e. social behavior, directed in response to the behavior of other people. M. Weber believes that the basis of the development of society lies in social activities. American sociologist and social philosophy expert - philosopher Tolcott Parsons (1902-1979) believes that society is a system based on the attitude of people bound by values and norms. A person carries out his social activities based on these. T. Parsons was, in a certain sense, M. Weber can be said to be an ideological heir. The famous philosopher P. A. Sorokin (1889-1968) defines society as an integral integrity, defined by the activities of individuals and social groups aimed at meeting their needs, resulting from their interaction with each other and with society. In his view, "for a society to exist, there must be at least two people, and they must be connected to each other in an interaction. This is the manifestation of the most ordinary society...». P. A. Sorokin

characterized society in terms of recognizing the diversity of sociocultural systems that are in complex motion in horizontal, vertical directions, and in the manner of fluctation (vibration).

Society is such a union of human beings that its integrity is ensured by social production, that is, by the joint activity of human beings in general, aimed at production, self-empowerment and reproduction [4, 509-510]. "Society is one whole socio-political organism, a change in each element of it, inevitably affects the other part.» [5, 51]

Hence, the concept of "society" covered the following meanings:

1. The concept of society reflects not only the activities of those who live now, but also their past and the life of future generations, from the very beginning of human history to its future.

2. This concept also finds expression in the specific aspects of Societies of a certain variety. For example, "Society of antiquity", "European Society", "Asian society", etc.

In this concept, societies that exist without being directly linked to each other are also expressed, in which aspects related to space and time are taken into account. Examples of these include ancient sacs, Central Asian societies, arab societies in the Middle East, or societies in Western Europe, among others.

Society as a social system performs the following functions:

- production of vital favors;
- systematization of production;
- * reproduction and human socialization;
- * distribution of Labor results;
- * ensuring compliance of state management activities with the law;
- * structuring political systems;
- * formation of ideologies;
- * ensuring the historical continuity of cultures and national-spiritual values.

In society, human and being, the interaction and interaction between people, social groups, classes, aimed at satisfying the vital needs of a person, on the basis of which lies the human interest. In fact, the meaning of human life is

formed on the basis of interests. Profit-the product of desire and need. The most primary interests consist of factors that are considered the necessary need for a person to lead a life. These factors appear to be material and spiritual. Satisfaction of personal needs, negativity does not occur outside of society. It is an objective necessity that self-interest is in the structure of communalism. The interest of the individual - in accordance with the interests of the community-is the basis for unity in this community, and in the approach to interests-commonality, and some personal interests arise from the specificity of the community, in other words, to the El, to the nation.

"Interest expresses interest in something real, demand. There is no disinterested person. It arises in the perception of the political self as the desire of the subject to improve socio-political life. People whose interests are close to each other quickly unite.» [6, 76-77]

On the basis of this, as the author points out, lies the goal of the perception of the interests of the people, the nation, raising national progress to a new level by satisfying them. Therefore, the basis of society lies in the interests of Man and him. Society arises only when a certain system, an internal device, is established that regulates any activities and relationships aimed at the implementation of the human interest. In the case of an imbalance in the interests of the individual and society, the criteria for social justice are violated. The strength of the community will be undermined. After all, society is for the individual, and in turn the individual is also a member of society. The French ally Ognyst Kont claims that society is a holistic social organism according to its origin and development, which depends on the development of subjects (individ, class, class). [7, 16] if there is no person, there will be no society, Society will have all its internal devices moved by the person, and in the process of its implementation, it will also socialize itself. The person, his realization that he is the force that organizes, moves, ensures his proportionality and controls these processes, which - from the point of view of sociality-is the basis for his approach to his

activities. When he directs his interests to social interests, his activity in social life increases. "Society is a set of social relations that are formed at a certain stage of the historical development of mankind. Within social relations, the most important thing is the relationship-economic relations, which determine the form of social consciousness... It is not correct to attribute the progress of society to economic relations as a whole. This is materialism. It is also necessary not to forget about the will, perseverance of people, the activities of historical figures, spiritual factors.» [8, 208]

Hence, social relations are a socially oriented view of the interests of the individual, the interaction and interaction between man and being, people, social groups, classes, aimed at satisfying the vital needs of a person. The study of the content of social relations that manifest and act in society shows that the components that apply to them are always valid within the framework of a complex of material and spiritual-ideological relations, that is, social relations with the attention of their essence are in material and spiritual content. Material social relations include relations of economic production. Formal relations include political, legal relations. Moral, ideological, religious and other relations are concentrated in spiritual relations. «...these manifestations of social relations that differ from each other will be permeated with originality and commonality, confrontation and unity in their content. While material and ideological relations have their own content as a social perception of human and social involvement based on the interests of the subjects, each does not act separately, in its pure form. Originality to the content of these manifestations of social relations, rather than confrontation, is a unity of commonality and unity between them.» [9, 81]

In society, certain functions of social institutions are reflected in social relations. Social relations are the relationship between people, social groups, Nations, Outer classes and other social structures and constitute their activities in the internal economic, social, political ideological

and cultural spheres. Separately obtained man is the initial element of society, social relations. The development of society is determined by the development of social relations. The main factor in social relations is social consciousness, its role in society is that it can manifest positive qualities or negative vices in the functioning of social relations.

CONCLUSION

The decrease in the position of spiritual and ideological relations in social relations, the norm of the content measure is manifested in this in the psyche of some members of society, illusions such as loquacity, indifference, immortality, bribery, selfishness, insolence and irresponsibility, vagrancy and groupliness, stupidity become established. The negative impact of this establishment on social relations is that situations can arise that hinder the development of the economic, spiritual, political and social spheres of society and threaten society.

"Even in economic relations – hidden economy; in social relations – localism and nationalism; in political relations - extremism; in spiritual relations - spiritual poverty; in legal relations – conditions for the formation and development of lawlessness and crime-arise due to the fact that these negative situations, which have formed and developed in the content of social relations on the totality of society.» [9, 81]

Therefore, it should be remembered that social consciousness in social relations between people, social groups, classes, nations, along with relations between man and society, citizens and the state, is practiced on the basis of national-spiritual and ideological factors.

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